

laboratory insects respond differently from field-reared insects, at least in flight performance. Second, the tropical field

population contained a proportion of adults capable of sustaining flights of long duration. Questions to be answered

include whether, how often, and under what conditions the BPH exploits this capability. ■

Soil and crop management

“Catch” crops for summer annual fallow

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Eight crops were evaluated to determine the most suitable as a local summer annual (catch) crop after winter rice. The experiment was in a replicated randomized block design and was continued for 3 seasons (1976-78). The test crops included sesame (locally called gingelly) — the traditional catch crop in the area — as well as short-duration tapioca, groundnut, cowpea, sweet potato, mung bean, finger millet, and black gram. During early growth the crops depended on residual soil moisture and, later, on occasional summer showers.

Performance of crops in summer rice fallow. Kayamkulam, Kerala, India, 1976-78.

Crop	Duration (days)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Returns ^b (US \$/ha)
Tapioca ^c	103 ^d	13.5	487
Groundnut	103	2.8	842
Cowpea	67	0.6	206
Sweet potato	103 ^d	2.8	132
Mung bean	66	0.2	61
Finger millet	103	0.5	123
Sesame	76	0.3	119
Black gram	78	1.3	394

^aMean for 3 seasons. ^bIn terms of the prevailing Kerala market rate. ^cGrown in only 1 season. ^dHarvested before full maturity.

Groundnut gave the highest returns (see table). Although it matures 20 to 25 days later than sesame, it can easily fit into the region's current cropping pattern. The 110-day interval between the winter and autumn rice crops is sufficient for a crop of 103 days duration. Tapioca and sweet potato require more than 110 days to mature.

The growth durations of black gram

and cowpea are similar to that of sesame; their input costs are low and their returns relatively high. Hence for the

local summer rice fallow, groundnut, black gram, and cowpea can be used as summer annual catch crops. ■

Improved management-practices for raising boro seedlings

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Cold temperature in the boro season (min, 10-12°C) retards and stunts the growth of seedlings, especially of modern rices, even if transplanting is delayed to

60 days after sowing. BRRI experiments indicate that improved seedbed management involving the use of farm-yard manure and night cover during the cold season can produce more vigorous seedlings. When transplanted at 30 or 45 days after sowing, such seedlings were taller, had higher dry matter production, and lower mortality. They produced higher yields in a shorter growth period than conventionally grown seedlings. ■

Root distribution and root biomass production of rice under different soil water regimes in Entisols of northern India

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Rice plants were grown in the greenhouse under four water management regimes: a) saturation (0-0.1 atm) throughout crop growth, b) saturation up to maximum tillering and flooding up to ripening, C) flooding up to maximum tillering and saturation up to ripening, and d) con-

tinuous flooding (water depth of 3 ± 5 cm) throughout crop growth. Plants were spaced 40 cm apart to keep their roots separate.

Horizontal root growth (distance between the plant base and the farthest root cores around the hill) was measured. Cores were taken from various lateral zones around the plant with a 2-cm-diameter core sampler. The roots were spray washed and separated from the cores.

The water management practices at the initial vegetative phase affected root distribution and root mass production

Root distribution and biomass of rice under 4 water regimes in Entisols, Varanasi, India.

Water regime	Root color	Intensity of distribution	Lateral spread (cm)	Vertical spread (cm)	Root biomass production (g/hill)
Continuous saturation	Deep brown	Sparse	13	26	12.2
Saturation + flooding	Brown	Less abundant	14	23	13.2
Flooding + saturation	Light brown	Abundant	16	18	15.6
Continuous flooding	Lighter brown	Dense mat	16	16	18.1

(see table). On flooded soil the root system was compact and developed horizontally. The roots were spread like a thick mat all over the superficial soil layers.

In the saturation regimes the rice

plants developed vertical root growth. Water roots or nodal roots that started at panicle initiation were absent but appeared in the flooded regimes.

The deep brown color of roots in the saturation regime may have been caused

by the formation of ferric compounds that coat root surfaces under oxidized conditions. The flooded regime favors the accumulation of ferrous compounds around the root surface and causes a light brown color. ■

Effects of foliar spray of *Azotobacter chroococcum* on rice

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Azotobacter chroococcum occurs in the phyllosphere of water hyacinth *Eichhornia crassipes*. The presence of *Azotobacter* spp. in the phyllosphere of several field crops, vegetables, and ornamental plants has been reported. An attempt was made to determine how the phyllosphere bacterium *A. chroococcum* that occurs with water hyacinth affects the rice crop.

The field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications in 1977–78 samba (Sep–Jan). A pure culture of *A. chroococcum* (phyllosphere bacterium of water hyacinth) was obtained from the

Effect of foliar spray of *A. chroococcum* on grain and straw yield of rice.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Grain yield		Straw yield	
	t/ha	Increase over control (%)	t/ha	Increase over control (%)
0–50–50kg NPK/ha	1.4	–	4.1	–
0–50–50kg NPK/ha + <i>Azotobacter</i> spray	1.7	7.6	4.5	9.0
50–50–50kg NPK/ha	2.2	37.3	5.6	36.4
50–50–50kg NPK/ha + <i>Azotobacter</i> spray	2.3	42.9	5.6	36.4
50–50–50kg NPK/ha + topdressing of 50 kg N/ha	2.4	49.6	6.8	63.6

^a Differences significant at 5% level. Grain yield: SE = 0.102. C.D. = 0.315. Straw yield: SE = 0.56. C.D. = 1.73.

Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi. The bacterium was grown in Jensen's nitrogen-free medium. The variety ADT31 was grown in a 5 × 4-m plot with various fertilizer treatments, both with and without *Azotobacter* spray. The rice plants were sprayed 3 times with a foliar spray of the *Azotobacter* culture suspension at 100 ml/m² (16 × 10⁸ cells/ml) on the 15th, 30th, and 45th day after

transplanting.

The foliar *Azotobacter* spray significantly increased grain and straw yields. The plots treated with 0–50–50 kg NPK/ha + *Azotobacter* spray yielded 7.6 and 9.0% more grain and straw, respectively, than the unsprayed plots (see table). Plots treated with 50–50–54 kg NPK/ha + *Azotobacter* yielded about the same as the unsprayed plots. ■

Azolla as a nitrogen source for rice in northeast Thailand

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The use of *Azolla pinnata* as a substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in rice was evaluated in a field trial. The experiment

was in a randomized complete block with four replications. Azolla was seeded at 312.5 kg/ha. Phosphorus was applied in solution with a watering can, and potassium was applied basally. Yield increases attributed to azolla were comparable to those attributed to applied nitrogen (see table). The treatment where azolla was incorporated into the soil after transplanting and that where it

was not were equally effective. Yields were similar when azolla was seeded before or after transplanting. One crop of azolla supplied at least 37.5 kg N/ha, equivalent to about 200 kg/ha of ammonium sulfate. ■

Response of RD7 rice to azolla and chemical fertilizers, Ubon Ratchathani Rice Experiment Station, 1979 dry season.

Azolla ^a	Treatment			Azolla fresh wt ^b (t/ha)	Rice yield ^c (t/ha)
	Fertilizer (kg/ha)				
	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		
0	0	25	25	0	2.3 b
0	18.5 + 18.5 ^d	25	25	0	3.4 a
Seeded after T	0	12.5 + 12.5 ^e	25	17.4	3.7 a
Seeded after T	0	12.5 + 12.5 ^e	25	18.1 ^f	3.7 a
Seeded 26 DBT	0	12.5 + 12.5 ^e	25	15.1 ^f	3.5 a

^a T = transplanting. DBT = days before transplanting. ^b 20 days after seeding (DS). ^c Any 2 means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^d Split at T and panicle initiation. ^e Split just after seeding and 10 DS. ^f Incorporated 20 DS.

Correction of zinc deficiency in direct-seeded rice

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Zinc deficiency in rice seedlings is common in Louisiana. It is usually corrected with a foliar application of zinc (Zn-EDTA). But stands of small seedlings are reduced severely before farmers recognize the deficiency and